

Detecting text duplicates with binary classification: Insights from logistic regression, random forest and xgboost

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Abstract:

Recently, there was a significant increase in the amount of large and bulky documents and textual data which requires efficient methods for identifying text duplication to maintain data integrity and quality. This paper provides insights of three supervised machine learning algorithms such as Logistic-regression, Random Forest, XG Boost for binary Classification of duplicate texts. Quora dataset is used to train all three models and also a tf-idf Vectorization is used for feature engineering. Each model's performance is measured depended on accuracy, precision, recall ,F1-score. Our finding reveals that all three models achieve close accuracy in identifying the duplicate texts, This means that for this particular problem, simpler methods such as Logistic Regression may be just as effective as more complicated techniques, such as XGBoost. This is an indication that while using models for the text deduplication task there is the need to look for a balance between the models' interpretability and computational costs as well as its accuracy, while further research is needed to explore the impact of various datasets, this work demonstrates the potential of supervised machine learning algorithm for binary classification for efficient text duplication.

Keywords: Binary classification, detecting duplicate texts, supervised learning, tf-idf vectorization, logistic-regression, Random-forest, XGBoost-algorithm, Machine-Learning.

1.Introduction:

Recent breakthroughs in Natural Language Processing and text mining have opened a door for many researchers in developing applications that leverage text classification methods, also due to rapid growth of digital content has led to an barrage of textual data[7]. This large amount of data has resulted in both challenges and opportunities. Detecting text duplication is a task that will benefits in improving accuracy and efficiency of SEO in digital marketing, academic integrity and in many more fields. Duplicates can arise from various sources which includes:

- Data Entry Errors: Human mistakes during data entry might result in the duplicate entries with minor changes.
- Web Scraping: When working with dynamic websites, web scraping tools may collect repeated content accidentally.
- Malicious Activities: Plagiarism and content scarping with malicious intent might result in an increase in duplicate content.

These factors had a bad impact on a data integrity. Traditional methods for duplication detection like review and rule-based systems and manual review are not efficient and has many errors. A machine learning approach for this problem is ideal , this paper will provide a insights of supervised learning such as Log-R, Random-Forest and XGBoost models. These models are trained using Quora DataSet that as undergone Data reprocessing, feature Engineering and Model training.

Supervised-ML is utilised for Binary grouping which learns from a labelled data to make a predictions for unseen data[13]. With respect to detecting text duplication , a dataset consists of pair of text which is labelled as "duplicate" and "not duplicate".

Logistic-Regression(LR) is a well known M-L algorithm that falls within the category of SML methods. It is a data analysis strategy that employs mathematics to discover relationship between two data elements and then uses these relationships to anticipate the value of one factor based on the other[11].

Random Forest: RF is a sort of SML approach that combines the outputs of numerous decision trees to produce a single result[6]. Its ease of use and adaptability have driven its adoption, since it can handle both classification task and regression difficulties.

XGBoost Algorithm: XGB is a scalable distributed-gradient-boosting decision tree(GBDT) machine learning tools.[14]

To perform Feature extractions of data there exist several techniques among one is TF-IDF Vectorization[1]. TF-IDF is a method of weighing a word/term that assigns a different weight to each term in a text, depending on the frequency of words per document and frequency of terms across all documents. Before applying this TF-IDF, it is required to perform few initial feature engineering process to gain a basic characteristics of the text which includes steps such as Text Length Calculation, Word Count, Common Word Count, Total Word Count and Word Share Ratio which eventually helps for models to understand the characteristics of a question pairs for betterment of prediction.

This work provides the insight of SML for detecting text duplication, in which we explore the use of LR, RF and XGB. The result will provide the valuable awareness into the effectiveness of these machine learning approaches.

2.Literature Survey:

Denis Eka Cahyaniet al[1]. As conducted a Emotional comparison between commuterline and Transjakarta consumers using multinomial Naïve-Bayes and Tf-idf model. They also performed a comparative analysis between TF-IDF vectorization and Word2Vec to check for which feature engineering technique is best suited for this task as a result this study showed that the TF-IDF modelling outperformed word2vec modelling in terms of classification accuracy.

Wael H. Gomaa et al[2]. present a detailed assessment on text similarity algorithms, classifying them as string based, corpusbased, knowledge-based. String-based measures concentrate on phrase patterns and character synthesis with algorithm like Damerau-Levenshtein and jaro-Winkler gaining prominence. Corpus-based similarity uses large corpora to identify the link between words, which involves methods like LSA and PMI. Knowledge based methods uses semantic networks to evaluate word similarity.

Justin Martineau et al.[3] presents a method for weighing word-based features in binary classification tasks, by demonstrating a accuracy enhancements across different problems. The proposed approach calculates the values based on ngram frequency and the difference in IDF between Training set both positive-negative. Using a SVM as a model and bag-of-words as feature engineering the study provides a insights into the efficiency of method and its potential.

Roshan Kumari et al.[4] presents a research paper which delve into binary classification with extracting information retrieval and extraction, crucial for predefined classes. It particularly addresses sockpuppet detection, a issue where accounts are labelled as either sockpuppets or non-sockpuppets, with a concern over fake identities and malicious activities. The study unify several approaches to binary classification, offering insights into its significance and application across various domains.

Maake Benard Magara et al.[6] the study investigates optimal algorithm and similarity metric combinations for recommender systems using no-linear classification algorithms and text similarity measures. Random Forest(RF), Recursive Partitioning(rpart) and boosted algorithms were evaluated. Cosine similarity outperformed other metrics. The proposed similarity metrics is a enhanced model development for Evaluating similarities and recommending solutions by discovering additional obstacles and issues.

K.Kowsari et al[7]. due to the rapid growth in complex documents and texts has intensive need for advanced machine learning methods to accurately classify texts. This study provides an overview of a text classification algorithms, which covers extracting text features, reducing the dimension of a data and evaluation techniques. It highlights the challenge of finding a suitable techniques for text classification by discussing the limitations and real-word applications.

J. Wang et al.[8] Measuring text similarity is an crucial task in NLP such as retrieving a information and machine translation. This paper reviews the current approaches categorising text similar measurement algo and also discuss following enhancements. This task is analysed by two factors: text distance and text representation.

C.Liu et al[9]. Study represents a method for automatic text classification using a word2vec for vector representation of feature words and an improved TF-IDF technique for weighting. Having combination of this weight also vector of a text, texts are classified through the collection of word vectors by addressing the challenges in traditional text classification techniques.

Wang et al.[10] Uses different form of naive-bayes and support-vector machine-algorithm for prose classification with varying performance by model features and tasks. This paper displays that word bigram features improve sentiment analysis, NB performs well compared to SVM on short snippets and novel SVM-variant utilizes N-B log-count proposition performs really well among tasks while sometimes achieving state-of-the-arts results.

S.H.Shetty et al.[11] As ML tends to enable computers to solve problems using data. This research paper talk through SML and its applications in classification and regression. Also explaining its importance of training and testing datasets. SML depends on skilled experts guidance by mapping inputs and outputs. It is widely used for characterizing data with larger training sets by improving its performance.

3.Proposed Methodology:

This section summarizes the key contributions which concentrates around the implementation of three different ML algorithms for a binary classification tasks. Logistic-Regression is empirical approach that estimates the likelihood of an instance belonging to a certain class based on input data. The Random-Forest classifier on the together is an ensemble learning techniques that constructs multiple decision trees and aggregates their predictions making it prone to overfitting and noise. XGBoost is a third algorithm which is highly efficient and expandable gradient boosting method which sequentially constructs an ensemble of poor prediction model with each model goal to provide a accurate result.

3.1 Logistic-Regression:

LR an sml which is used for grouping of datasets. It estimates on a given set of independent variables the likelihood that an instance belongs to a particular class. It is employed both classification and regression tasks as paper is focused on binary classification LR evaluates output of a reliant variables[11] and the result is a integer value. It includes true or false, yes or no etc. But instead of giving a exact values as zero or one, it provides the Bayesian values between 0 and 1.

3.2 Random-Forest Classifier:

RF is supervised learning algo which combines a outcomes of a multiple decision trees to obtain a single output or a prediction. This ensemble learning technique strong matches the power of “the wisdom of crowds” by combining a predictions of various base decision trees to improvise the predicting performance and control the chance of over-fitting. For pair of texts the trained RF model will provide a output as duplicate or not duplicate but the end decision is dependent on the more voting from all the ensembled decision trees in the forest.

3.3 XGBoost algorithm:

XGB also called as Extreme Gradient Boosting which is a type of boosting a evolved from the previous gradient-boosting approach. It is a technique developed to improve the speed of computing, scalability and performance of a model. XGB operates particularly on a numeric vectors. The prediction of a model at every step updates iteratively as the goal of this model is to prevent a prone of overfitting achieved by minimizing an objective function that involves a loss function which measures a accuracy of prediction and coordinating terms that deals with a complexity of a model[14].

For a text duplicate detection task this three model classify a pairs of a text questions into duplicate and non-duplicates. The models are strengthened with a numerical features which are extracted from a text data(Quora Dataset) which is done using TF-IDF vectorization. By tuning a Hyper parameter where it is required these models are trained for checking the performance of a SML for a NLP tasks.

4. Implementation:

The implementation section provides a complete overview of a research topic which includes detailed explanation of a dataset, includes structures and key features. Data preprocessing includes handling the missing

values, feature engineering and vectorization. Splitting data into training and testing sets by making use of stratification for model training for LR, RF and XGBoost which involves their unique parameters and training processes. Evaluation of a models are measured using accuracy, precision, Recall and F1score. Hyperparameter approaches such as random search and final report comparing model performances.

4.1 Data Preprocessing:

The dataset utilized for the study contains of a question pairs from Quora[15] which is aimed at detecting a duplicate questions. To prepare a data for modelling, handled missing values and engineered features such as question length of q1 and q2, Common word count to measures the number of words that are common between question1 and question2 which helps in detecting questions that is duplicate based on shared vocabulary.

Fig 1

In the Fig1 a histogram shows the distribution of question frequency as it is preferred to see the insights of a dataset, as the chart display on x-axis it represents the number of times questions repeated in dataset where as y-axis(on a logarithmic scale) displays the frequency of the occurrences. The logarithmic scale on y-axis helps us to visualise the distribution more clearly especially when we have a larger variations in the frequencies.

As we can see in the chart a questions which are unique or occurred once in a dataset are 10^5 as we can see through the number questions there is a particular question repeated 160 times in a dataset visualising a this insights of data will definitely helps in Data preprocessing.

4.2 Feature Engineering:

Feature Engineering is crucial for transforming a raw text data into a format which is suitable for ML models and before implementing a TF-IDF vectorization a several features were engineered to capture the characteristics of these questions, such as:

- Question length
- Common word count
- Total number of words in both questions

4.2.1 TF-IDF vectors:

TF-IDF is a way of weighing a word or a phrase which gives a distinct weighs for every term in a documents or a dataset dependent upon the frequency of terms in each docs as well as frequency of terms across docs. TF-IDF utilized in this study because improves performance by improving recall and precision values[11]. The significance of a word grows in proportion to how many times it appears in the document (corpus). TF-IDF can be explained as:

- Term Frequency (TF) measures the amount of times a term T shows up in a document D . It is calculated using following formula,

$$tf_{t,d} = \frac{f_{t,d}}{\sum_k f_{t,d}} \quad (1)$$

Where $f_{t,d}$ is the frequency of term t in document d and the denominator is the total number of terms in document d .

- Inverse Document Frequency (IDF) metrics assesses the amount of information provided by a indicating whether it is common or rare across texts. IDF calculated using following formula,

$$idf_t = \log\left(\frac{N}{|\{d \in D: t \in d\}|}\right) \quad (2)$$

In which N is the total value of docs in the corpus and the denominator represents the value of documents containing the term 't'.

- TF-IDF score: TF-IDF score calculated for a term t in a doc d is as follows,

$$tfidf_{t,d} = tf_{t,d} * idf_t \quad (3)$$

When it comes to implementation of this in a detection of duplicate text 'tfidfvectorizer' is used from a 'sklearn.feature_extraction.text' module to calculate a tf-idf scores for a particular dataset. Where only two columns that is question1 And question2 columns from dataset are considered and it transforms the text data into a tf-idf matrix where each term is weighted according to its frequency in a document and its inverse frequency across the corpus.

4.2.2 Dimensionality Reduction Using Truncated SVD:

High-dimensional features in an text data can lead to several prones which includes increased computational expenses and the risk of over-fitting. Over-fitting occurs when a predictor learns noise in the data instead of the actual signal which can effect the performance on a unseen data. To solve these issues we applied Truncated Singular Value Decomposition(SVD), technique that reduces the dimensionality of the TF-IDF matrix while maintaining its structure and relationships.[1]

SVD is linear algebraic method that decomposes a matrix X into three smaller matrices and it is represented as:

$$x \approx U \Sigma v^T \quad (4)$$

- Where X is the original matrix that is tf-idf matrix.
- U is an $m * k$ which is an orthogonal matrix m is the count of documents and k is count of reduced dimensions.
- Σ is $k * k$ diagonal matrix containing the singular values.
- V^T is $k * n$ orthogonal matrix, n is number of terms.

Singular values within Σ represents importance of each dimensions by retaining only the top K singular values it will reduce the dimensionality of X to K while retaining the most significant information by allowing to capture the underlying structure of the data without the noise present in the higher-dimensional space.

4.3 Model Training and Evaluation:

After performing feature engineering models are trained with the data where the vectorised features are combined with remaining features and stored in X and target variable 'is_duplcaite' is stored in y variable. 'Train_test_split' splits the data into group that trains and test according to specific 'test_size' which is set to 80:20 indicating 80% of data is training data and 20% is test data.

The LR model was trained on a dataset with features which is stored in X_{train} and the target variable is stored in y_{train} . After training the model is used to predict outcomes on the test set X_{test} which results in predicting y_{pred} . The model's working was examined using accuracy, classification report. These metrics provides a detailed insights into the model's prediction capacity.

Random Forest a versatile ensemble method that provides high accuracy and reduce overfitting by combining multiple decision trees. In this context RF classifier was developed using a portion of training data. 10% of training data was used to build model. The trained model was then used to predict the outcomes on the test set X_{test} which results in predictions. Key components include bootstrapping samples like each tree is taught on a random sample with replacement from the training set, random feature selection like at each split random sub_set of features which is taken for dividing which decorrelates the trees and for classification the final prediction is based on majority voting of all trees.

XG_Boost is improved distributed gradient boosting library designed to be highly efficient, flexible and portable. XGB builds an ensemble of decision trees by training each and every tree to correct the errors of the previous trees in the sequence. The key aspect here is to control the loss function by adding new models that predict the errors of a previous models and then by combining them to make the final prediction. It includes regularization terms to prevent overfitting and increase the performance of the model, it supports parallel processing making it faster compared to other boosting algorithm.

4.3.1 Evaluation Metrics:

Several metrics are used for evaluating performance of ml model, with a particular metrics for classification tasks particularly focus on accuracy score, classification report which includes precision, recall and F1 score are metrics with respect to models we trained that is LR, RF classifier and XGBoost algorithms.

Accuracy Score:

The accuracy score measures how much time model correctly classifies the outcomes, accuracy is straightforward metric that indicates the acc as a whole of the model's predictions. Accuracy score is defined as follows:

$$\text{Acc} = \frac{\text{TP} + \text{TN}}{\text{TP} + \text{TN} + \text{FP} + \text{FN}} \quad (5)$$

In which:

TP: True Positives(the number of accurately anticipated positive situations)

TN: True Negatives(the number of accurately anticipated negative situations)

FP: False Positives(displaying num of mistakenly anticipated positive cases)

FN: False Negatives(displaying num of mistakenly anticipated negative instance)

Classification Report:

A classification report gives a detailed description of a model's performance across different metrics such as precision, recall and F1 score.

Precision: Precision is the ratio which tells correctly expected positive gains to the total expected positives, it indicates the accuracy of the predictions. It is defined as:

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}$$

Recall(Sensitivity): Recall is proportion that accurately predicted positive observations to all the actual positives. It evaluates the model's ability to find positive instance.

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}$$

F1-Score: A score of F1 is the balanced average of precision and recall providing a balance between precision and recall it is particularly beneficial for unbalanced datasets.

$$\text{F1-score} = 2 * \frac{\text{Precision} * \text{recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{recall}}$$

Confusion Matrix: CM is a specific layout that visualizes the performance of algorithm. It displays the counts of true positives, false positives and false negatives which gives insight into the types of errors made by the model.

Metric	Logistic Regression	Random Forest	XGBoost
Accuracy	0.74	0.74	0.73
Precision(macro)	0.72	0.72	0.75
Recall(macro)	0.69	0.70	0.66
F1-Score(macro)	0.70	0.70	0.67
Confusion Matrix			
True Positives(TP)	15306	15830	11529
True Negatives(TN)	44277	43892	47663
False Positives(FP)	6749	7134	3363
False Negatives(FN)	14526	14002	18303

Table 1. Performance Evaluation Results

5. Results and Discussion:

5.1 Results: statistical performance analysis of the three classifier models namely the logistic regression, the random forest classifiers and the XGBoost showed that all three models were fairly accurate with the LR and the random forest classifiers equally accurate at approximately 0.74 whereas XGBoost got slightly lower at 0.73.

Class	Metric	LR	RF	XGB
0	Precision	0.75	0.76	0.72
	Recall	0.87	0.86	0.93
	F1-Score	0.81	0.81	0.81
1	Precision	0.69	0.69	0.77
	Recall	0.51	0.53	0.39
	F1-score	0.59	0.60	0.52
Total	Support(class 0)	51026	51026	51026
	Support(class 1)	29832	29832	29832
	Accuracy	0.74	0.74	0.73
	Macro avg Precision	0.72	0.72	0.75
	Macro avg Recall	0.69	0.70	0.66
	Macro avg F1-score	0.70	0.70	0.67
	Weighted avg Precision	0.73	0.73	0.74
	Weighted avg Recall	0.74	0.74	0.73
	Weighted avg F1-score	0.73	0.73	0.77

Table 2. Detailed Classification Report

Logistic Regression showed strong performance in positive class with precisions and recall of 0.75 and 0.87 respectively while showing weaker performance in negative class with precision of 0.69 and recall 0.51. Random Forest showed a slightly better balance between positive and negative classes with precision of 0.76 and recall of 0.86 respectively. XGBoost with the lowest overall accuracy at 0.73 showed the highest precision in negative class with 0.77 but lower recall at 0.39 in positive class it achieved precision =0.72 and recall=0.93 resulting in an F1-score of 0.81 overall XGBoost showed a lower overall accuracy and recall.

5.2 Discussion:

The results indicate that all three classifiers that is Logistic Regression, Random Forest and XGBoost have their respective strengths and weakness. Logistic Regression and Random Forest achieved the highest accuracy but their precision, recall and F1-score shows a significant differences. Logistic Regression was strong in identifying positive classes but struggled with negative classes indicating potential bias towards the majority class. Random forest showed a better balance between precision and recall likely due to its ensemble nature. XGBoost while having the highest precision for the negative class, exhibited lower recall and a lower F1-score suggesting it might be more conservative in its predictions. Despite this XGBoost's strong performance in terms of precision for the positive class and overall macro average precision suggests it is effective at correctly identifying positive instance. But for also building a better model using an advanced Feature engineering models like BERT will help model to improve its performance.

6 Conclusion:

The research analyzed the working models three machine learning algorithms, Logistic_Regression, Random_Forest, and XGBoost, in finding duplicate texts from the Quora dataset. The results say's that Logistic Regression and Random Forest achieved similar accuracy rates of 0.74, indicating that simpler models can perform on par with more complex techniques like XGBoost. However, precision and recall metrics revealed nuanced differences. Logistic Regression excelled in identifying positive instances but had lower performance in detecting negative instances, indicating a bias towards the majority class. Random Forest balanced precision and recall more effectively due to its ensemble nature, reducing overfitting and capturing a broader pattern in the data. XGBoost, while having the highest precision for non-duplicates, showed lower recall, particularly for positive instances, leading to a lower overall F1-score. The study emphasizes the importance of choosing the right model based on accuracy, interpretability, and computational efficiency. Future research should explore advanced feature engineering techniques and evaluate these models on different datasets to gain deeper insights into their generalizability and robustness in various text duplication detection scenarios.

7. References:

- [1] Denis Eka Cahyani, Irene Patasik, "Performance comparison of TF-IDF and Word2Vec models for emotion text classification" Vol. 10, No. 5, October 2021, pp. 2780~2788
- [2] Wael H. Gomma, Aly A. Fahmy, "A Survey of Text Similarity Approaches" Volume 68– No.13, April 2013
- [3] Justin Martineau, Tim Finin, Anupam Joshi and Shamit Patel, "Improving Binary Classification on Text Problems using Differential Word Features" MD 21250 18 August 2009
- [4] Roshan Kumari, Saurabh Kr. Srivastava, "Machine Learning: A review on Binary Classification" Volume 160 – No 7, February 2017
- [5] V.Srinivasan "Feature Selection for Share Market Dataset Using Entropy And Information Gain, Journal of Applied Science and Computations, Volume 6, Issue 4, Page No:144-149, April-2019, ISSN NO:1076-5131.
- [6] Maake Benard Magara, Sunday O. Ojo, Transo Zuva, "A Comparative Analysis of Text Similarity Measures and Algorithms in Reseach Paper Recommender Systems" March 2018 DOI: 10.1109/ICTAS.2018.8368766
- [7] Kamran Kowsari, Kiana Jafari Meimandi, Mojtaba Heidarysafa, Sanjana Mendu,Laura Barnes, Donald Brown, "Text Classification Algorithms: A Survey" 23 April 2019
doi:10.3390/info10040150
- [8]Jiapeng Wang and Yihong Dong, "Measurement of Text Similarity: A Survey" 31 August 2020
doi:10.3390/info11090421

[9] Cai-zhi Liu, Yan-xiu Sheng, Zhi-qiang Wei and Yong-Quan Yang, “Research of Text Classification Based on Improved TF-IDF Algorithm” 978-1-5386-7416-1/18/\$31.00 ©2018 IEEE

[10] Sida Wang and Christopher D. Manning, “Baselines and Bigrams: Simple, Good Sentiment and Topic Classification” 8-14 July 2012

[11] Shruthi H.Shetty, Sumiksha Shetty, Chandra Singh, Ashwath Rao, “Supervised Machine Learning: Algorithms and Applications” February 2022, DOI:10.1002/978111982190B.ch1

[12] V.Srinivasan “Mean Centroid K-Means Clustering Based on Boundary Region Analysis for Share Market Database”, CiiT International Journal of Digital Signal Processing, Vol 12, No 1, pp-1-7, January 2020

[13] M. Aruna, S. Sukumaran, V. Srinivasan MITS Hybridization of Fuzzy Label Propagation and Local Resultant Evidential Clustering Method for Cancer Detection International Journal of Engineering Trends and Technology, ISSN-2231-5381, Vol.70, issue-9, Page: 34-46, September 2022.IF.0.16

[14] Sharmeen Binti Syazwan Lai, Nur Huda Nabihan Binti Md Shahri, Mazni Binti Mohamad,

Hezlin Aryani Binti Abdul Rahman, Adzhar Bin Rambli, “Comparing the Performance of AdaBoost, XGBoost, and Logistic Regression for Imbalanced Data” March 21, 2021

DOI: 10.13189/ms.2021.090320

[15]<https://www.kaggle.com/c/quora-question-pairs/data>